

PHYSICAL AND ECONOMIC WATER PRODUCTIVITY OF DIFFERENT CROPS IN PAITHAN LEFT BANK CANAL
COMMAND OF JAYAKWADI IRRIGATION PROJECT IN MARATHWADA REGION OF MAHARASHTRA

Kamble S. H.¹, Guledagudda S. S.², Kulkarni G. N.³, Patil R. H.⁴, and Shirahatti M. S.⁵

College of Agriculture, Dharwad-580005, Karnataka, India

kamblesh77@gmail.com

(MS Received: 26.11.2023; MS Revised:30.12.2023; MS Accepted:02.01.2024)

MS 3156

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURE)

Abstract

Present study attempts to measure physical and economic water productivity in Paithan Left Bank Canal command of Jayakwadi irrigation project in Maharashtra. The findings of the study revealed that the productivity of crops grown in the head region was less as compared to middle and tail regions of the canal due to excessive use of canal water. The physical water productivity was lower at the head region as compared to middle and tail regions in all the crops because of prevalence of flood and furrow irrigation methods. Similarly, the economic water productivity was also lower in the head region compared to middle and tail regions.

Keywords- water productivity, crops grown, irrigation methods.

Introduction

The world is facing an unprecedented water crisis and among the different key factors two basic factors are influencing water management issues in agriculture. The first factor is agricultural sector which is the largest user of freshwater in the world (Molden, 2007) and the other is net returns from the water use in agriculture sector are the lowest as compared to other competing uses (Scheierling et al., 2014). In the next three decades the global food systems will require 40-50 per cent more freshwater than today. Municipal and Industrial demand for water will increase by 50-70 per cent during this period. India is facing high water stress and the country is amongst those with the most fragile and uncertain water resources in the world. Irrigation sector with almost 78 per cent share dominates the present and future water use scenario in India. One of the main response to these emerging challenges is to focus on improving water productivity in agriculture, as even small improvements could have large implications for local and national water budgets and allocation policies. This view is shared by Global Water Partnership (2000), UNESCO (2009) and FAO (2012, 2016) which consider demand management as an important option to cope with water scarcity, with improving agricultural water productivity as the single most important avenue for managing water demand in agriculture. Land, labour and water are the most critical factors influencing agricultural production. However, unlike land and labour productivity, the concept of Water Productivity (WP) though existent from a long time, became prominent only recently especially in the developing countries (Barker et. al., 2003). Water productivity is of two types, i.e. physical water productivity and economic water productivity. Physical water productivity (kg/m^3) is the ratio of agricultural output to the amount of water consumed from all available sources including irrigation, rainfall etc. (kg of produce per cubic metre of water consumed and economic water productivity (expressed as Rs/m^3) is the ratio of value of crop output to the amount of water consumed or to the amount of irrigation water applied by the farmer. In view of this, an attempt has been made to assess the physical and economic water productivity of different crops grown in Paithan Left Bank Canal command of Jayakwadi Irrigation project in Marathwada region of Maharashtra.

Methodology

Jayakwadi irrigation project was purposively selected for the study as it is one of the largest earthen dams in Asia and is located around 52 km away from Ch. Sambhaji Nagar in Maharashtra. Paithan Left Bank Canal (PLBC) of Jayakwadi project was also purposively selected as irrigable command area under PLBC was more than 75 per cent, of the total irrigable area of the project. Under PLBC, irrigation demand of the command area is fulfilled through a total of 70 distributaries. To get representative sample of the whole command area of the canal system, three distributaries representing head, middle and tail reach of the PLBC were selected for study. Each selected distributaries were also divided in the three regions, viz. head, mid and tail reaches and 20 farmers from each zone were randomly selected for the study. Thus, from each distributary, 60

farmer respondents who are beneficiaries of the irrigation project were selected. In this way from three distributaries a total sample of 180 farmer respondents were selected. To assess the profitability of different crops grown in the command area, primary data were collected from 180 sample farmers through well-structured pre-tested interview schedule. The quantity of water used by the farmers to cultivate a particular crop in a season was estimated. The quantification of water used by the farmers in different crops was measured using 90° V-notch and the observations were taken in different intervals of time. After taking the observations, the quantity of water discharged from FIC was calculated using the formula $Q = 1380H^{2.5}$ where Q is quantity of water discharged from FIC; H is height of water in centimeters from crest of V-notch. Then, the physical as well as economic water productivity was estimated using the following formulae.

Physical Water Productivity (kg/m^3) = Y/W

Where,

Y -Yield of crop per hectare of land (kg)

W- Total volume of water used (m^3) and

Economic Water Productivity ($\text{Rs.}/\text{m}^3$) = P_y/W

Where,

P_y - Overall value of yield from one hectare of land

W- Total volume of water used (m^3)

Results and discussion

Quantity of water used for irrigating different crops

Quantification of water was done only for *rabi* and summer season crops and results are presented in Table 1. It is noticed from Table 1 that, quantity of water used for irrigating the different crops was decreased from head reach to tail reach. Tail reach farm were receiving less water than head and mid reach farms. Off course, head reach farms were taking positional advantage. In case of wheat crop, at head reach, quantity of water used for irrigation purpose was $7057.56 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$ which decreased to $2731.43 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$ at tail reach farm. At an overall level, average water used for wheat crop was measured to $4973.36 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$. Similar trend was noticed in case of all the crops. In case of chick pea, average quantity of water used for irrigation purpose at overall command was $1864.71 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$. Similarly, for sorghum, tomato, groundnut, green chilli and sugarcane, average irrigation water use was $2205.88 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$, $4395.29 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$, $2903.52 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$, $5762.88 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$, and $16865.78 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$, respectively.

Productivity of different crops cultivated in PLBC

Productivity of different crops cultivated at head, mid and tail reach of PLBC are presented in Table 2. Table revealed that, average productivity of wheat crop at overall level was recorded to $2544 \text{ kg}/\text{ha}$. From head to tail reach productivity of wheat was decreasing. Similarly, productivity of chick pea at overall level was estimated to $1390 \text{ kg}/\text{ha}$. Maximum productivity was recorded at mid reach of the canal. In case of sorghum, maximum productivity ($2277 \text{ kg}/\text{ha}$) was estimated at head reach which was decreased to $1965 \text{ kg}/\text{ha}$ and $1937 \text{ kg}/\text{ha}$ at mid and tail reach, respectively. In case of tomato, increasing trend in productivity was observed from head to tail reach. At head reach productivity of tomato was $28563 \text{ kg}/\text{ha}$ was recorded which

increased to 29678 kg/ha at mid reach and 30897 kg/ha at tail reach. At overall level it was found to 29713 kg/ha. In case of groundnut, similar trend like tomato was observed. At overall level productivity of groundnut was recorded to 2128 kg/ha. In case of green chilli, at mid reach level, productivity was recorded to be maximum while lowest was recorded at tail reach. With respect to the sugarcane, decreasing trend was observed, i.e. at head reach maximum and at tail reach minimum productivity was recorded. At overall level, productivity of sugarcane was 90347 kg/ha.

Physical water productivity of different crops in PLBC command area

Physical water productivity of different crops grown in PLBC command was calculated, as per the procedure cited in methodology and results are presented in Table 3. It is seen from Table 3 that physical water productivity with respect to all crops grown in PLBC command during *rabi*, summer and annual crops showed increasing trend from head reach to tail reach of the canal. In case of wheat crop, physical water productivity was ranged from 0.39 kg/m³ to 0.88 kg/m³ from head to tail reach, and at overall command area it was estimated to 0.51 kg/m³. In case of chickpea crop same was ranged between 0.58 kg/m³ to 1.06 kg/m³, and at overall level it was estimated to 0.75 kg/m³. With respect to sorghum crop also, physical water productivity was ranged from 0.84 kg/m³ to 1.07 kg/m³, with 0.93 kg/m³ at overall command area. Similarly, in case of groundnut, at head reach physical water productivity was found to 0.67 kg/m³, at mid reach it was 0.70 kg/m³ while at tail reach it was 0.90 kg/m³. With respect to the green chilli and sugarcane, similar trends were estimated. At overall command area, physical water productivity of green chilli was 1.62 kg/m³ and in sugarcane, it was estimated to 5.36 kg/m³.

Economic water productivity of different crops in PLBC command area

The results of economic water productivity of different crops grown in PLBC command area are shown in Table 4. It can be seen from the Table 4 that economic water productivity was also increasing from head to tail region with respect to all crops. In case of wheat crop at head reach, economic water productivity was estimated to Rs. 9.71/m³, while at mid reach it was Rs.11.68 / m³ and Rs. 20.92 / m³ at tail reach. At overall command area an economic water productivity was estimated at Rs.12.44 / m³. Similarly, economic water productivity of chick pea was ranged from Rs.2.80 / m³ at head reach to Rs. 55.13 / m³ at tail reach, with Rs. 37.16 / m³ of irrigation water at overall command area. With respect to sorghum, at overall command area, economic water productivity was estimated at Rs. 25.27 / m³, which ranged in between Rs. 21.55/m³ to Rs. 30.94/m³ from head reach to tail reach. Similarly, economic water productivity of tomato was estimated to Rs. 58.92 / m³ at overall command which ranged in between Rs.48.71 per m³ to Rs.66.02 per m³ from head reach to tail reach of canal. In case of groundnut, one cubic meter of water was producing Rs. 33.75 at overall command whereas, in case of green chilli it produced Rs. 42.75 and in sugarcane crop one cubic meter of water generated an income of Rs. 12.56, at overall command.

Conclusions

The findings of the study revealed that the productivity of crops grown in the head region was less compared to middle and tail regions due to excessive use of canal water (among different reasons) by the head region farmers. Therefore, there is a need to construct the cement lined field leading to see pipe irrigation channels which

prevent excess canal water entering the farmers' field. Further, farmers need to be educated about the actual crop water/irrigation requirements for different crops through extension activities.

1.The physical water productivity was lower in the head region as compared to middle and tail regions in all the crops because of prevalence of flood and furrow irrigation methods. Hence, farmers need to be encouraged to use micro irrigation methods such as sprinkler and drip irrigation systems to not only save water but to increase water productivity.

2.The economic water productivity was also lower in the head region compared to middle and tail regions. Hence, to enhance the economic water productivity the irrigation water charges need to be collected on quantitative basis on the volume of water used from the farmers to ensure optimum utilization of canal water.

References

- Basediya S S, Pyasi S K and Shrivastava R N, 2018, A study on farmer response for technical intervention in canal command area of Samrat Ashok Sagar project. *International Journal Current Microbiology Applied Science*, 7 (3): 3387-3401.
- Gulati A and Mohan G, 2018, Towards sustainable, productive and profitable agriculture: Case of rice and sugarcane. *Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations*, pp. 1-72.
- Mandal K G, Mohanty R K, Ghosh S, Kundu D K, Raychaudhuri M, Padhi J, Majhi P, Sahoo D K, Ashwani K and Ambast S K, 2016, Participatory water management and integrated farming in a canal command. *ICAR-Indian institute of water management (formerly Directorate of Water Management), Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India*, 75 (1): 1-64.
- Molden, D., Oweis, T. 2007. Pathways for increasing agricultural productivity. In. *Water for Food, Water for Life, Comprehensive Assessment of Water Management in Agriculture*, ed. David Molden. London: Earthscan, and Colombo: International Water Management Institute.
- Poddar R, Ejaz Qureshi M and Shi T, 2014, A comparison of water policies for sustainable irrigation management: The case of India and Australia. *Water resource manage*, 28 (1):1079-1094.
- Scheierling, Susanne M. & Treguer, David O. & Booker, James F. & Decker, Elisabeth, 2014. "How to assess agricultural water productivity ?looking for water in the agricultural productivity and efficiency literature," Policy Research Working Paper Series 6982, The World Bank.
- Sharma B R, Gulati A, Mohan G, Manchanda S, Ray I and Amarasinghe U, 2018, Water productivity mapping of major Indian crops. *A Report Submitted to NABARD*, pp.1-213.
- Sivasankar A, Reddy B and Ravi Kumar K, 2014, Low economic efficiency of irrigation water resource in Krishna Western delta of Andhra Pradesh demanding water management interventions. *Journal International Academic Research for Multidisciplinary*, 2 (1): 527-545.
- Sultanapur V, Patil S S, Hiremath G M, Reddy B S and Ayyangoudar M S, 2016, Economic water productivity of paddy in TBP and NRBC command areas of Karnataka. *Journal of Farm Science*, 29 (4): 526-528.

Table 1. Quantity of water used in different crops of PLBC

Sl. No.	Crops	Quantity of water used (m ³ /ha)			
		Head reach	Middle reach	Tail reach	Overall
1.	Wheat	7057.56	5131.08	2731.43	4973.36
2.	Chick pea	2378.08	1907.41	1308.65	1864.71
3.	Sorghum	2701.23	2108.61	1807.81	2205.88
4.	Tomato	5387.25	4047.87	3750.74	4395.29
5.	Groundnut	3478.98	3127.09	2104.48	2903.52
6.	Green chilli	8504.96	5032.41	3751.26	5762.88
7.	Sugarcane	20514.73	17519.07	12563.53	16865.78

Table 2. Productivity of different crops in PLBC command area

Sl. No.	Crops	Productivity (kg/ha)			
		Head reach	Middle reach	Tail reach	Overall
1.	Wheat	2747	2507	2403	2544
2.	Chick pea	1374	1408	1387	1390
3.	Sorghum	2277	1965	1937	2060
4.	Tomato	28563	29678	30897	29713
5.	Groundnut	2317	2178	1888	2128
6.	Green chilli	9799	10108	8089	9332
7.	Sugarcane	99315	89967	81758	90347

Table 3. Physical water productivity in PLBC command area

Sl. No.	Crops	Physical Water Productivity (kg/m ³)			
		Head reach	Middle reach	Tail reach	Overall
1.	Wheat	0.39	0.49	0.88	0.51
2.	Chick pea	0.58	0.74	1.06	0.75
3.	Sorghum	0.84	0.93	1.07	0.93
4.	Tomato	5.30	7.33	8.24	6.76
5.	Groundnut	0.67	0.70	0.90	0.73
6.	Green chilli	1.15	2.01	2.16	1.62
7.	Sugarcane	4.84	5.14	6.51	5.36

Table 4. Economic water productivity in PLBC command area

Sl. No.	Crops	Economic Water Productivity (Rs./m ³)			
		Head reach	Middle reach	Tail reach	Overall
1.	Wheat	9.71	11.68	20.92	12.44
2.	Chick pea	2.80	36.23	55.13	37.16
3.	Sorghum	21.55	25.17	30.94	25.27
4.	Tomato	48.71	65.92	66.02	58.92
5.	Groundnut	30.16	32.05	42.21	33.75
6.	Green chilli	32.10	52.33	54.06	42.75
7.	Sugarcane	11.45	12.62	14.31	12.56